

**The entrepreneurial willingness of the professional training interns in
Morocco. Case of OFPPT LARACHE**

**L'intention entrepreneuriale des stagiaires de la formation professionnelle
marocaine. Cas de L'OFPPT Larache**

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Abstract

The present article aims to describe, explain and even predict the entrepreneurial willingness amongst interns of the Office of the vocational training and the promotion of the work (OFPT) trainees, according to a validated model.

Our problematic is part of a theoretical framework of social dimensions developed by A. SHAPERPO and L. SOKOL (1982), and it's based on the psychosocial theory of planned behaviour of I. AJZEN (1991). AJZEN (1991); to tackle the main question of this research paper we have opted for a hypothetico-deductive paradigm as for the methodology choice, basing our process on the verification of a range of hypotheses provoked by Larache as a local range for the research; as for the hypotheses, three main groups of factors have been identified : The first group of factors includes the attitudes associated with behaviour via the existence of a more or less formal draft of a project, The second group contains the subjective norms manifested by the need for achievement, the search for autonomy, the willingness to take risks and the existence of entrepreneurial role models to follow, the last factors tested are shaped by perceptions of behavioural control embedded in work experiences, entrepreneurship education and the availability of financial, information and advisory resources.

The analysis of these three groups of factors allowed us to define a model of entrepreneurial willingness. This model was assessed on a population of 189 trainees of the OFFPT professional training in Larache.

Keywords: « Entrepreneurial willingness »; « Attitudes »; « Subjective norms »; « perceptions of behavioural control ».

Résumé

L'objectif de cet article est de décrire, expliquer et prévoir selon un modèle validé, l'intention entrepreneuriale des stagiaires de l'Office de la Formation Professionnelle et de la promotion du travail (OFPT). Notre problématique s'inscrit dans un cadre théorique des dimensions sociales développé par A. SHAPERPO et L. SOKOL (1982), et trouve ses fondements sur la théorie psychosociale de comportement planifié de I. AJZEN (1991). Notre méthodologie est de nature hypothético-déductive elle se base sur la vérification d'une panoplie d'Hypothèse dans la localité de Larache. Trois groupes de variables sont retenus pour la validation de nos hypothèses. Le premier groupe de variables comporte les attitudes associées au comportement par l'existence d'une idée d'un projet plus aux moins formalisé. Le deuxième groupe, contient les normes subjectives matérialisée par le besoin d'accomplissement, la recherche de l'autonomie, la propension à la prise de risque et l'existence de modèles d'entrepreneur à imiter. Les dernières variables testées sont formées par les perceptions du contrôle comportemental contenues par les expériences professionnelles, l'enseignement de l'entrepreneuriat et la disponibilité des ressources financières, d'information et de conseils. L'analyse de ces trois groupes de variable nous a permis de définir un modèle d'intention entrepreneuriale. Ce modèle est validé auprès d'une population de 189 stagiaires de la formation professionnelle OFFPT à Larache.

Mots clés : « Intention entrepreneuriale » ; « Attitudes » ; « Normes subjectives » ; « perceptions du contrôle comportemental ».

Introduction:

This article aims to explore and deepen the topic of entrepreneurial willingness among the trainees of the OFPPT in Larache as a preliminary step to the creation of enterprises.

Entrepreneurship is an act that is generated within a process of construction. Several researchers have tried to understand the causes that lead people to become entrepreneurs, however, we are convinced that, in order to understand the act of starting a business, we need to examine, deeply, the entrepreneurial willingness.

In fact, the creation of enterprises represents today an important economic and social asset in the world. It is considered as the momentum of any country's economic development; based on this fact, Morocco and since the 1990s has implemented stimulating entrepreneurial programmes, which reflects a political determination to place the entrepreneur at the heart of the state's transition policies in the era of neo-liberalism. In the current paper we will mainly focus on the behavioural aspect of the aspiring or the entrepreneurs to be, as they represent capitalist agents in Morocco, and to be more precise, we will be targeting our research efforts on examining the upstream phase that precedes the entrepreneurial process within the interns that follow a professional training course in the "OFPPT" institute of Larache; all with aims of capturing a clearer image about the global capacity of the professional training in the making of future entrepreneurs.

Indeed, it is only appropriate to examine the upstream processes that comes beforehand the creation of any enterprise, as this phase provides an inclusive read through data since we won't eliminate those who didn't manage to make real their enterprise creation aims; actually, examining the behavioural background behind enterprises' creation is deemed inseparable from examining the intentions and willingness that stimulates individuals to pursue the entrepreneurial path.

Matter of fact, a retrospective view of the willingness to entrepreneur, demands a hypothetico-deductive paradigm that focuses mainly on the willingness or intention aspect; N. F. KRUEGER (2000), have previously stressed that entrepreneurship is beyond all, remains an intentional process that requires the use of well adapted conclusive paradigms that concerns entrepreneurs and future entrepreneurs equally; Hence, through the present paper we are trying, not only to describe, but rather explain how the willingness to entrepreneur is formed amongst individuals that pursue a professional training course in Larache, Morocco.

Our research is based on a key idea, which is to understand the influence of individual and contextual factors on the emerging entrepreneurial willingness amongst the trainees of the OFPPT in Larache. This prompts us to ask the following questions:

“What psychological, socio-cultural and contextual factors can positively influence the entrepreneurial willingness in Morocco?”

In order to address this question, we will first review the literature regarding the different factors that explain the entrepreneurial willingness. Subsequently, we explain the methodology adopted by outlining the choice of our sampling frame as well as the tests used to validate the hypotheses. We then present and analyse the results concerning the different explanatory factors of the entrepreneurial willingness of the professional training interns, in Larache.

1. Literature review and hypotheses developing:

The hypotheses formed in our research aim to explain the impact of factors that are behavioural attitudes relative, subjective norms relative, and factors related to perceptions of the behavioural control on the willingness to entrepreneur; eventually these hypotheses allowed us to claim the use of a hypothetico-deductive research model. The framework of the proposed model is mainly within the SHAPERO and SOKOL's (1982) context of the social dimensions of entrepreneurship, moreover, it builds on AJZEN's theory of behavioural prediction.

The willingness to entrepreneur is more likely to be explained through factors of attitude, factors of subjective norms such as motivation, social influence...etc, and perception factors as in the accessibility to resources, more clearly:

- The attitudes that are behaviour relative indicate the existence of a project idea that might be less or more formal.
- The subjective norms are driven by motivations such as the need to feel accomplished, the desire to be independent, these norms are also stimulated by risk taking and knowledge of the entrepreneurship models.
- The perception of behavioural control refers to the entrepreneurial capacities, the accessibility or difficulty to access resources such as information, counselling etc.

1.1. Research context: Education and training programme of entrepreneurship in the “OFPPT” institute.

Recently, youth have been facing significant struggles in debuting a career and obtaining a job, on the other hand, creating job opportunities remains as a major challenge that the government faces, hence, it has been recently sought that empowering the youth is what would enable them to make an entrance happen into the highly competitive environment that job market is,

moreover, it will stimulate the desire and willingness to entrepreneur within them ; within this context, the entrepreneurial education is deemed crucial as it tackles the development of the entrepreneurial culture, capacities and skills amongst the youth.

The International Labour Organization (ILO) regards entrepreneurship as an opportunity to create decent and sustainable employment., indeed the development of entrepreneurial skills enhances access to employment opportunities for youth.

Within the same sense, the "Understanding Business" programme initiated by this organisation aims to educate young people about the world of entrepreneurship and improve both their entrepreneurial and business mindsets and skills. The programme is structured into nine units provided by facilitators affiliated to professional training institutions or universities and it has been introduced into the national education systems and training programmes in more than twenty countries.

The CLE programme was first introduced to the Office for Professional Training in May 2008, and ever since, it has attracted the interest of the Office as an opportunity to boost the promotion of youth employment and to reinforce the support to enterprise creation especially for the graduates of these institutes. Hence, it has been decided to introduce this programme during the professional training courses in order to enrich the unit or subject of “ raising entrepreneurship awareness”; also, it has been agreed with the director of research and training engineering t, upon the adaptation of a rather general and generic version of the CLE programme accordingly to the Moroccan context and requirements of the OFPPT, all while respecting the original format of the programme; not to mention that the adapted version of the programme is to be taught as a subject to both levels of training / education that the OFPPT offers : technicians and specialised technicians alike.

1.2. Specification of the research hypotheses: Explanatory factors for entrepreneurial willingness:

Through the present paper, we are focusing on examining the impact of the factors we have previously mentioned, as following: factors related to attitudes, related to behaviour or subjective norms, and related to perceptions of behavioural control, on the willingness to entrepreneur amongst the trainees of the OFPPT institute in Larache. In this respect, we are to introduce a certain range of hypotheses in order to fulfil a hypothetico-deductive research paradigm within the context of the social dimension of both A. SHAPERO et L. SOKOL (1982), including AJZEN (1991) theory on the planned behaviour. For those solemn purposes,

we are collecting data via a survey that folds into four themes and ten dimensions through forty-five questions.

Firstly, we are to tackle the attitudes linked to behaviour, subjective norms afterwards and finally the perceptions on the behavioural comport; tackling this aspect is ought to be the first step before introducing any paradigm/model that attempts to explain and examine the willingness to entrepreneur as for each concept contains a wide range of factors that needs to be examined in details. Following this thread of logic will allow us a global vision of the entrepreneurial willingness model.

1.2.1. Behaviour relative attitudes:

The concept of attitude is deemed crucial in the study of entrepreneurship willingness and intention, in fact, the concept itself, put simply, is the evaluation of a specific object within our social or physical environment.

The notion of attitude is most often put forward as part of a three-component model: cognitive, affective and behavioural (Olson, MA and Kendrick, RV, 2008); the cognitive aspect of attitude is based on beliefs, thoughts and the characteristics associated to the attitude itself. Indeed, the affective dimension is based on feelings towards a person or emotions associated with the subject of the attitude, which can vary positively or negatively (B. ZAJONC, 2008).

Nonetheless, attitudes can also have a conative or behavioural origin that is rooted in the individual's actions towards a certain object.

In fact, the will or intention to entrepreneur depend on the behavioural dimension, hence, the will or the intentions are an excellent link between attitudes and intended behaviour; nonetheless, the entrepreneurial willingness depends on the conceptualisation of a project idea. Based on what have been mentioned so far, we are to proceed with the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: The existence of a formal idea or enterprise project has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial willingness of interns.

Hypothesis 2: The search for relevant information in order to make real and concrete certain aspects of the idea or enterprise project positively influences the entrepreneurial willingness of the interns.

1.2.2. The subjective norms:

The second range of factors related to the planned behaviour theory are the subjective norms; simply put, the subjective norms are the beliefs that an individual develop regarding creating an enterprise. In other terms, and according to the planned behaviour theory, an individual's willingness to entrepreneur depends on how they deem a behaviour to be conform to the

entrepreneurial values; in Morocco, the subjective norms are mainly acquired through the familial and professional background, in this sense, we are mainly talking about the social pressure that a group of people apply on an individual: friends, family members, work colleagues etc.

The submission motivation refers to the will and desire of an individual to submit or to refute submission to peer pressure, in fact the subjective norms are determined by the normative beliefs and the motivation to act accordingly to some else's opinion. (GERGEN K.J, GERGEN M.M & JURTA S, 1992). The submission motivation can push individuals to shape their attitudes to the most fitting ones according to the peers they are in contact with, and the degree of this influence is determined by normative beliefs, and the later are determined by the others' vision of what should be done.

The subjective norms do take various formats, they can be expressed in various forms: form of motivation, form of risk-taking attitude or they can appear through the knowledge of the entrepreneurs' models.

Based on what have been mentioned so far, we are to proceed with the following hypotheses as well:

Hypothesis 3: The need for accomplishment influences the entrepreneurial willingness positively.

Hypothesis 4: The search for independence influences the entrepreneurial willingness positively.

One of the personality traits that have been previously mentioned in the literature review is the risk-taking ability, it's a dimension related to the subjective norms as well and it can be influenced by social factors and the direct environment (E. J. Douglas & DA. Shepherd, 2001); it's mainly a psychological trait in the research of entrepreneurial willingness, specifically according to E.J. Douglas & R. Riajman (2001). Based on this knowledge, we are to proceed with the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 5: Risk-taking attitude influences the entrepreneurial willingness of professional training trainees in Larache.

Moreover, the existence and knowledge of entrepreneurial role models within a family, close or distant circle, can encourage OFPPT trainees to invest, in fact, in a similar previously conducted research, it has been shown that over than half of the population investigated come from a family of entrepreneurs; Hence, we are to proceed with yet another hypothesis:

Hypothesis 6: Familiarity with entrepreneurial role models positively influences the entrepreneurial willingness.

1.2.3. Perception of the behavioural control:

Perceptions of behavioural control are split into perceptions of one's own entrepreneurial capabilities and the perceptions of the resources available from the environment (information, counselling and finance).

According to BIRD-SCHOONHOVEN C. et ROMANELLI E (2001), the intentions or willingness involve entrepreneurial that enables verifying the feasibility of a project, the latter is justified by entrepreneurial education and professional experience; and according to Krueger et Carsrud (2000), the entrepreneurial education reinforces the perceptions of entrepreneurial skills.

In fact, the Moroccan agents can only be interpreted and explained within a Moroccan context, according to their own proper resources and limits; this context affects the enterprise spirit specifically in the logical construction of the agents; indeed, the perception of skills and the availability of resources (accessibility to resources) frames how aspiring entrepreneurs define their investment strategies.

According to B.J. BIRD (2001), the willingness to entrepreneur demands a personal will and skills that assures the viability of a project's idea. However, the pro-entrepreneurial attitudes alone are not enough to form entrepreneurial intentions or willingness, they must be combined with a perception of competence, which enable the examination of the feasibility of an entrepreneurial act (J. VESALAINEN and T PIHKALA, 1999).

In order to verify if an educational background on entrepreneurship or enterprise creation are factors that might impact the perceptions of entrepreneurial skills of project holders, or more, enable the idea of entrepreneurship to emerge, we are ought to proceed with the following hypothesis as well:

Hypothesis 7: Perceptions of entrepreneurial skills that individuals acquire through entrepreneurial, or enterprise creation education positively influences the entrepreneurial willingness.

As for the concept of skill must be matched by the concept of experience. After all, work experience is a contributing factor that can reinforce entrepreneurial willingness, in fact, there has been numerous research that assumes the existence of a positive correlation between the willingness to entrepreneur and the number of professional experiences in enterprises, Hence, it is a must to proceed with the following hypothesis as well:

Hypothesis 8: Work experience strengthens the entrepreneurial willingness.

As for individuals that feel able to control their environment develop enough self-confidence and perseverance to make real their entrepreneurial ideas; meanwhile it's the other way round for extroverts who lack self-confidence. In fact, the ability to control the environment is ineffective if individuals can perceive overwhelming obstacles that confuse them and make them risky and therefore undesirable. Thus, the entrepreneurial willingness requires that obstacles are manageable and that resources are available. Therefore, we are ought to proceed with the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 9: Perceptions of resource availability positively influence the entrepreneurial willingness

2. Research methodology:

The aim of this paper is to link the theoretical framework to the practical one which consists of ensuring a connection between theoretical aspects and data collection through methodological approaches.

2.1. Research model choice:

In our research, we are opting for G.A. CHURCHIL's (1979) method of constructing measuring instrument of the multi-scale survey-type; according to this method, we will be able to reduce the shortcomings that a survey elaboration presents, as well as the multidimension and reliability of measures.

We will be forwardly presenting the process adopted for the verification of the reliability of the scales of measurements chosen in the present paper; however, it is a must to mention that we will be opting for the Churchill paradigm, and in order to develop a measurement scale according to the Churchill paradigm, we will have to go through four main phases:

- Specify the field of the construct: the conceptual model of the research was developed from the literature review.
- Generate a sample of items: the survey items are derived from the literature review and, above all, from the theoretical contributions on the entrepreneurial willingness.
- Collecting data: the data is collected through the survey.
- Purify the measures: based on the Principal of Component Analysis (PCA), and the calculation of the reliability through Cronbach's alpha.

2.2. Establishing the sample frame:

Our research is based on a sample of trainees in their second year at the OFPPT institute in Larache, at the ST, T and Q levels. In total we retained 189 analysable and nearly exhaustive

surveys with a response rate of 95%; then we have proceeded to insert answers into the SPSS software for further analysis. we input these answers on the SPSS software.

The survey was conducted between May 23rd and 31st, 2022. The sample consisted of 189 alumni trainees graduating in the year 2022/2021, the population studied is of 50.8% female trainees, and 49.2% male trainees and future graduates; as for the choice of this specific sample, it can be justified by the following reasons:

- Second year OFPPT trainees are chosen because they were several weeks away from debuting their careers and already having various career intentions.
- - The second-year trainees are selected because they have enough skills and cognitive abilities to ease their assimilation and comprehension in order to properly respond to the survey questions.
- - The second year OFPPT institute's trainees were selected because their environment indicated that their attitudes, subjective norms and perceptions could develop and reinforce their entrepreneurial willingness and intentions.
- - The OFPPT institute trainees have received basic training in management, accounting and project management, which will technically ease the creation of a new enterprise for them (especially in the fields of business management, commerce, corporate accounting, finance and accounting).
- - They have concluded their internships in enterprises, which will allow them to adapt their projects to the reality of the business sphere.

Therefore, our sample is a simple random sample, set according to the probabilistic technique, and it involves a true random draw, meanwhile the probabilistic technique gives each element of the population a known, non-zero chance of being selected.

2.3. Analysis of the choice of the sampling frame

Thanks to the database provided by the administration of the professional training institute of Larache, we have managed to obtain a list of the target population, we use a random sample because it is more reliable and allows us to estimate the population parameters with a certain degree of reliability since it is based on the laws of probability, since a multitude of research have previously demonstrated that a simple random sample is properly representative sample. The table below is a representation of the level of representativity of our sample in comparison to the population targeted; meanwhile the latter consists generally of the second-year trainees of the institute, all levels of education included. The total of the population targeted is 304 trainees, divided according to the education/training levels and majors as the following:

Table 1: The number of trainees of the second year enrolled in “EFP” Larache, and the level of representativity of the sample compared to the target population (source: the administration of “EFP” Larache).

Training level	Majors	2 nd year Trainees	Number of filled out surveys per trainee in the major	The Level of representativity in (%)
ST	Enterprise management / Technician specialised in enterprise management	85	35	41,18
	Digital development / Computer development specialised technician	19	17	89,47
	Technician specialised in commerce	23	16	69,57
	Finance and Accounting Specialised Technician	23	21	91,30
	Technician specialised in executive secretarial work	18	12	66,67
T	Administrative Assistant / Enterprise Accounting Technician	29	28	96,55
	Industrial Maintenance Electricity Technician	18	16	88,89
Q	Motor vehicle repairer	22	18	81,82
	Industrial maintenance electricity	35	13	37,14
	Electromechanics	32	13	40,63
Total		304	189	62,17

Source: Authors ‘own proceedings/ based on the data provided by the administration of the OFPPT institute of Larache.

The sample was computed with the help of a simulator on the following website:

<https://fr.checkmarket.com/calculateur-taille-echantillon> , based on the following factors:

- N: the size of the research population N=304 according to the data provided by the administration of the professional training institution.
- The 95% reliability level: a rate that indicates the degree of certainty with which the population will choose a response between a two given values.
- - The margin of error (reliability interval) at 5%: a rate that indicates the extent to which the survey results are likely to reflect the opinion of the overall population.

According to the stimulator, the required size of our sample should be of 170 trainees to be surveyed; as for the statistical analysis of the survey data, all has been processed through the SPSS v24 software using the following statistical tools:

- The Principal Component Analysis (PCA).
- -Cronbach's alpha coefficient.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The impact of attitudes associated to behaviour on the willingness to entrepreneur

The entrepreneurial intention or willingness as a factor to be explained is affected by attitudes. The latter are manifested by the existence of a, more or less formal, idea of a business project and by the search for information to make it concrete in a proper manner.

Hypothesis 1: The existence of a formal idea or enterprise project has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial willingness of interns.

Hypothesis 2: The search for relevant information in order to make real and concrete certain aspects of the idea or enterprise project positively influences the entrepreneurial willingness of the interns.

3.1.1. The influence of having a more or less formal idea of a project

The impact of the existence of a business idea or project on entrepreneurial willingness is verified by the one-factor analysis of variance technique (ANOVA); it's a statistical technique used in the case of a non-metric explanatory factor (the emergence of an idea) and a metric explanatory factor (entrepreneurial willingness or intention).

The data collected indicate a highly significant influence ($F = 25.562$ and $sig. = 0.000$) of the existence of a business idea or project on entrepreneurial willingness and intention, in a way that the more business projects or ideas students establish, the stronger their entrepreneurial

willingness and intention. Thus, hypothesis 1 is not refuted for the sample, so we accept the first hypothesis.

3.1.2. The influence of information research on the entrepreneurial willingness

The simple regression analysis allows the identification of significant links between information seeking and the will to entrepreneur, this analysis is deemed suitable for quantitative explanatory and explanatory factors.

The multiple R² is significantly different from 0 in the sample studied. At the threshold $\alpha = 0.05$, the critical value of F is between 3.89 and 3.90 for 1 and 173 degrees of freedom; knowing that the F calculated ((17,892, sig. = 0,000) is significantly higher, we can conclude that the quality of the fit provided by the regression is significant; hence, we can affirm the existence of a relation between the information seeking or research and the will to entrepreneur, Thus, we shall accept and confirm hypothesis 2 based on the results of the simple regression test.

3.2. The effects of the subjective norms on the entrepreneurial willingness

3.2.1. The influence of the need for accomplishment on the entrepreneurial willingness

The impact of the need or desire of accomplishment have been previously worded into the third hypothesis as the following:

Hypothesis 3: The need for accomplishment influences the entrepreneurial willingness positively.

According to the results of the principal component analysis, it has been revealed that the need for accomplishment has two components, the first one is concerned with psychological motivation which encloses the " taking responsibility ", " self-realisation " and " taking on the challenge " items, and the second component is about financial motivation which is made of the following items " earn more money " and " I will have the power ". In fact, these two explanatory and predictive factors are operating as quantitative factors, so simple regression analysis is required.

The simple linear regression showed a satisfactory association between the achievement needs represented by the psychological motivation and the entrepreneurial willingness; indeed, the intensity of this relation was evaluated at 24.00% (R). The share of variance in entrepreneurial intention explained by this need is 5.8%. Thus, the quality of the fit of the relation obtained by simple regression is deemed acceptable. As for the dependency, it is significant (the calculated value of F is higher than the critical value observed on the statistical table: calculated F =

10.667; sig. = 0.01 < (0.05); critical F is between 3.89 and 3.90, at the threshold $\alpha = 0.05$ for 1 and 174 degrees of freedom).

Regarding the second aspect of need for accomplishment, that corresponds to financial motivation, the result of the simple regression analysis indicated a weak link between the need for accomplishment represented by financial motivation and entrepreneurial willingness; indeed, the intensity of this relation is evaluated at 02.70% (R). The proportion of the variance in entrepreneurial willingness explained by the need for accomplishment is equal to -0.05%. Thus, this relation between entrepreneurial willingness and financial motivation is not significant, which can be explained by the lack of financial responsibility amongst our sample, given the very young age of most trainees at the OFPPT institute in Larache (79% of the trainees are under 22 years old), therefore, we conclude that the third hypothesis is accepted.

3.2.2. The influence of the independence seeking on the entrepreneurial willingness

According to the normality test result, the distribution of the data does not conform to a normal distribution, since (significance of p-value is less than 0.05) so null hypothesis stating the normality of the data can be rejected, thus we conclude that the data does not follow a normal distribution; and for those specific reasons, we are to opt for the Spearman rho correlation test. In this respect, we can safely conclude that there is little to no correlation between entrepreneurial willingness and the search for independence. This can be explained by the early age of the trainees (more than 79% are younger than 22 years) and the fact that they are not exposed to the job market yet. Hence, the fourth hypothesis is refuted.

3.2.3. The influence of the risk-taking attitude on the entrepreneurial willingness

The result of the PCA shows that there are two components that we call "FAILURE" and "UTILITY" factors. So, the effect of risk-taking on entrepreneurial willingness is manifested by a positive (utility) or negative (failure) perception according to the consequences of the collapse of the company that the trainee will create. Since these are quantitative factors, we will regress the entrepreneurial willingness on each of both factors.

The linear regression test has highlighted the relationship between failure as negative perceptions of the consequences of the collapse of an enterprise and entrepreneurial willingness. The acceptable value for the correlation coefficient is 48.9% and the value of the coefficient $\beta_1 = -0.492$ is negative, meaning that if the value of the negative perception (failure) increases, the intention decreases and vice versa.

The negative influence of failure on the entrepreneurial willingness and intentions are highly significant, since the value observed of the coefficient F (57,671 pour un sig. = ,000) is majorly

superior on the critical value between 3.89 and 3.90 at the $\alpha = 0.05$ threshold, for 1 and 184 degrees of freedom; moreover, the regression of entrepreneurial intention against positive perceptions of the consequences of the enterprise's collapse (represented by utilities) indicates a positive correlation. Indeed, the quality of fit obtained by this linear relationship is significantly acceptable and is evaluated at 4.373 for a sig. = 0.038. As such, the observed value of F is superior to the critical value F, estimated between 3.89 and 3.9 at the $\alpha = 0.05$ threshold, for 1 and 183 degrees of freedom.

We can safely state that the perceptions of failure of a creating an enterprise have a negative impact on the will to entrepreneur, while on the opposite, the positive perceptions vary in the opposite direction of the trainees' intentions to entrepreneur. In fact, the more negatively trainees perceive the consequences of the enterprise's collapse, the lower their will to entrepreneur, and vice versa: The more positively they perceive these consequences, the higher their entrepreneurial willingness and intentions; Hence, we conclude that the fifth hypothesis that states the following “**Risk-taking attitude influences the entrepreneurial willingness of professional training trainees in Larache.**” is valid and accepted.

3.2.3.1. The influence of the entrepreneurs' models knowledge on the entrepreneurial willingness

In order to test the sixth hypothesis that states the following “**Hypothesis 6: Familiarity with entrepreneurial role models positively influences the entrepreneurial willingness.**”, we are opting for the one-way one factor ANOVA technique, hence, we divided these entrepreneurial models according to whether they were part of the trainees' close circle, and for those specific cases of our sample, the result of Levene's test of homogeneity came out negative with a degree of significance (0.08) lower than 0.05, means the ANOVA technique is not applicable. Therefore, hypothesis 6 is refuted.

3.3. The effects of the perceptions of the behavioural control on the entrepreneurial willingness

The impacts of perceptions of behavioural control on the entrepreneurial willingness are manifested through the skills that students acquire through training at the professional training institute, and the skills that they develop through work experiences, therefore, we are to exhaustively examine the validity of the corresponding hypotheses.

3.3.1. The influence of the entrepreneurial skills' perceptions acquired through education

These perceptions are subsequently finalised in the form of a quantitative factor, consequently, a simple regression test is to be carried out in order to examine the seventh hypothesis that states the following: **“Hypothesis 7: Perceptions of entrepreneurial skills that individuals acquire through entrepreneurial, or enterprise creation education positively influences the entrepreneurial willingness.”**

The quality of the fit of the derived relation is acceptable and the dependency is statistically significant. The obtained value of the F-coefficient (28.296 for a sig. = .000) is well above the critical value between (3.90 and 3.92), at the threshold $\alpha = 0.05$, for 1 and 147 degrees of freedom). Therefore, hypothesis 7 is confirmed.

3.3.2. The influence of the availability and accessibility of resources on the entrepreneurial

The ninth hypothesis that has been previously established, states the following **“Hypothesis 9: Perceptions of resource availability positively influence the entrepreneurial willingness”**, The principal component analysis (PCA) of perceptions of resource availability allows us to identify two types of perceptions: perceptions of availability of information and counselling on one hand, and perceptions of availability of financial resources on the other. Both factors are quantitative in nature, so we a simple linear regression analysis is to be conducted.

The results of the regression of the entrepreneurial willingness and intentions versus perceptions of availability of information and advice show a rather remarkable correlation with a value of $R = 0.295$, the R^2 score (coefficient of determination) representing the percentage of variance of entrepreneurial willingness, which can be explained by the variance of perceptions of availability of information and advice, the quality of fit obtained by this linear relation is evaluated at $F = 17.529$ for a sig. = 0.000, is highly significant, the critical value of F (between 3.89 and 3.90 according to the table of the Fisher Snedecor distribution at the threshold $\alpha = 0.05$, for 1 and 184 degrees of freedom. Meanwhile, the results of the regression of entrepreneurial intention against perceptions of the availability of financial resources indicate a correlation with a coefficient of 23.2%.

The R^2 value (coefficient of determination), that is the percentage of variance in entrepreneurial willingness interpreted by the variance in perceptions of financial availability is estimated around 5.4%, the quality of the fit resulting from this linear relation is estimated at $F = 10.501$

for a sig. = 0.001 and is highly significant, the critical value of F (between 3.89 and 3.90 according to the Fisher Snedecor table at the threshold of $\alpha = 0.05$, for 1 and 185 degrees of freedom. Therefore, and according to the results of the regression of entrepreneurial intention against the two elements of the availability perceptions, we can confirm that hypothesis 9 is accepted and valid.

3.3.3. Work experience strengthens the entrepreneurial willingness

The influence of work experience on the entrepreneurial willingness and intentions is to be examined via the one-factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) technique, adapted to the case of a qualitative explanatory factor: work experience and a quantitative explanatory factor: the entrepreneurial intention. The significance degree, after the test, was set at 0.208, therefore work experiences have no influence on the entrepreneurial intention in our studied sample's case, thus hypothesis 8 that states the following **“Work experience strengthens the entrepreneurial willingness.”** Is refuted.

3.4. The simultaneous effects of the quantitative factors on the entrepreneurial willingness.

The simultaneous influence of all quantitative explanatory factors on the entrepreneurial willingness is determined by multiple regression. This is an expansion of simple linear regression involving several independent factors. It makes it possible to explain variations in the dependent variable based on several independent factors, that are assumed to be the source of these variations. Moreover, it makes it possible to evaluate the intensity of this association, we will proceed with multiple regression since they offer the possibility of examining the contribution of each of the explanatory factors to the interpretation of the phenomenon studied (J.-L. Giannelloni and E. Vernet, 2001).

The quantitative factors that are more likely expected to explain and predict entrepreneurial willingness among the trainees are:

- Researching information in order to formalise certain aspects of the enterprise idea or project.
- The psychological motivation to carry out a project.
- The Financial motivation and desire for power.
- Independence seeking.
- The risk-taking attitude, expressed in negative or positive perceptions of the consequences of the collapse of the enterprise that the trainees are to create.

- The Perceptions of the entrepreneurial skills that trainees acquire with entrepreneurship programmes and training.
- The perceptions resources availability and accessibility: financial resources, information and counselling.

In order to estimate the influence of these joined factors on the entrepreneurial willingness, we will proceed with multiple regression, of which the results are as following:

Tableau 2: Multiple regression of entrepreneurial willingness in comparison to all quantitative factors

ANOVA ^a						
Model	Sum of squares	Ddl	Average square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	55,264	9	6,140	12,813	,000 ^b
	Residue	60,384	126	,479		
	Total	115,647	135			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Non-standardised coefficients		Standardised coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Standard error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-,067	,060		-1,123	,264
	q6 information seeking to better shape aspects of the idea	,246	,064	,271	3,854	,000
	q7.1 and 3 and 5 psychological motivations for carrying out a project	,019	,065	,020	,283	,777
	q7.2 and 4 financial motivations and desire for power	-,088	,069	-,088	-1,283	,202
	q7 Independence seeking	,002	,065	,002	,027	,979
	q13 Negative perceptions on failure	-,444	,067	-,474	-6,639	,000
	q13 Positive perception on Utility	,099	,073	,094	1,354	,178
	q9.3 perceptions of entrepreneurial skills acquired through training at the institute	,053	,073	,054	,725	,470
	q11 perceptions of the availability and accessibility to resources: information and counselling	,095	,074	,090	1,274	,205
	q11 perceptions of the availability of financial resources	,136	,064	,147	2,138	,034
a. Dependent factor q12 entrepreneurial willingness						

Source: Authors’ own proceedings (Via SPSS)

The model is of satisfactory quality since the nine independent factors provide an explanation for almost half of the variance of the dependent factors in the initial data.

The FISHER-SNEDECOR coefficient F equal to 12.813 (sig. = 0.000) confirms the goodness of fit of the model, as it is well above the critical value given by the statistical table, the value of F is between 1.93 and 1.94 for $\alpha = 0.05$ and 9 and 126 degrees of freedom. We can state that the quality of the fit attained by multiple regression is significant.

In fact, to evaluate each contribution to the overall interpretation of the model, we calculated the value of the partial regression coefficient Beta. This expresses the expected evolution of the factor to be explained when one explanatory factor "changes by one unit", while the other explanatory factors "remain constant or controlled"; Nevertheless, in this analysis, what counts the most are the standardised regression coefficients (the "Coefficients" part of the table above), which are calculated on precisely the same basis as the non-standardised coefficients, but it is assumed that all the factors included in this analysis have been reduced", i.e. reduced to a mean of zero and a standard deviation of 1.

The examination of the values of this coefficient showed that the failure and UTI factors involving risk-taking attitudes, with continuous contributions of -0.474 and 0.094, remained the factors that best interpret the entrepreneurial willingness, followed by the information-seeking factor with a contribution of 0.271. The factors related to the perceived availability of "financial" and "information and advice" resources had values of 0.147 and 0.090 respectively; while the factors related to perceptions of the availability of "financial" and "information and counselling" resources had values of 0.147 and 0.090 respectively, and the factor of perceived entrepreneurial skills acquired through entrepreneurial training in the professional training institute had a contribution of 0.054 ; lastly, and in the same respect, the psychological motivation and independence-seeking factors contributed to the overall explanation of the model with the scores of 0.020 and 0.002 respectively.

Within the same context, to express which of the factors have significantly affected the entrepreneurial willingness, we performed the STUDENT test for each regression coefficient; and based in the values reported for T , the factors "information seeking", "risk-taking attitude", "failure and utility", "perceptions of availability of financial resources, information and counselling" contribute significantly to the explanation of the entrepreneurial willingness with a maximum risk of error of 0.215 for each of them.

In contrast, the effects of the factors 'psychological motivation'; 'financial motivation and desire for power'; independence seeking' and 'perception of the entrepreneurial skills acquired through the entrepreneurial training at professional training institute' are not significant.

Indeed, to be fully effective, the multiple regression technique must be supported by a significant independence between the explanatory factors, meaning there should be no significant correlation between them.

To conclude, we can assume that based on the calculations we have made opting for different statistical techniques, six of the nine hypotheses established have been regarded valid, consequently we can propose a valid model of the entrepreneurial willingness or the will to entrepreneur within our research sample.

Conclusion:

For our research, we have adopted a multitude of techniques: simple regression, multiple regression and the one way one factor ANOVA test in order to test the validity of the hypotheses we have established over the course of the present paper, these techniques have allowed us to focus on the explanatory and predictive factors of the entrepreneurial willingness or intentions amongst the trainees of the OFPPT institute of Larache. Eventually, we have conducted quantitative analysis to further identify and describe those factors that significantly influence and affect the entrepreneurial willingness.

The aim of this article is to analyse the attitudes associated with behaviour, subjective norms and perceptions of behavioural control through the nine hypotheses that have been set out in order to develop an explanatory model of the entrepreneurial willingness that is most fitting and appropriate to the professional training institute and that responds to the characteristics of the local population of Larache, Morocco.

The hypotheses testing analysis (one-way ANOVA, simple regressions and multiple correlation) of the influence of the explanatory factors on the target factor have enabled us to validate six hypotheses and refute three out of the nine hypotheses established.

The valid and accepted hypotheses are as following:

Hypothesis 1: The existence of a formal idea or enterprise project has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial willingness of interns.

Hypothesis 2: The search for relevant information in order to make real and concrete certain aspects of the idea or enterprise project positively influences the entrepreneurial willingness of the interns.

Hypothesis 3: The need for accomplishment influences the entrepreneurial willingness positively.

Hypothesis 5: Risk-taking attitude influences the entrepreneurial willingness of professional training trainees in Larache.

Hypothesis 7: Perceptions of entrepreneurial skills that individuals acquire through entrepreneurial, or enterprise creation education positively influences the entrepreneurial willingness.

Hypothesis 9: Perceptions of resource availability positively influence the entrepreneurial willingness.

The validity of the model we have developed can be a subject for critic related to the validity of external scales; Nonetheless, in our case, the validity is limited by time and financial resources. Indeed, to ensure external validation and validity, it is necessary to refer to studies on samples from different institutions and different countries. In fact, the verification will strengthen the validity of our results, and consequently, contribute to their widespread use, even though the cultural diversity, population size and access to information make external verification almost a mission impossible. However, we are to mention that comparing results is only possible if the models tested are similar and the methods used for the verification tests are the same.

Our research can initiate a continuum of the entrepreneurial process, as it will enable us to expand knowledge about entrepreneurship, the decision-making phase by examining the transition from the will to entrepreneur to action, asking the following question:

What factors might sustain the entrepreneurial willingness and intentions towards the act of realisation?

Put more simply, our aim is to explore the analysis and description of entrepreneurial acts as an initiating behaviour in the downstream entrepreneurial process.

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